

Case Report

Effects of a 10-week Pilates-Based Exercise Program on Trunk Control, Balance, and Gross Motor Skills on a Young Girl with Diplegic Cerebral Palsy: A Case Report

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Abstract

Background: Children with cerebral palsy (CP) can have deficits in postural control and overall movement that impact their performance in daily activities. Pilates consists of stretching, strengthening, and coordination exercises. A few studies have demonstrated the benefits of Pilates on postural control deficits in children with CP over the age of seven. Pilates offers a safe and fun activity for children.

Case Report: The purpose of the case study was to implement a modified Pilates exercise (MPE) program with a child with CP and investigate its effects on her trunk control, balance, and gross motor (GM) skills. The subject of the case report was a 6-year-old student with a diagnosis of diplegic CP with moderate impairments. She completed a 10-week MPE 30-minute program focused on core strengthening with an emphasis on upper and lower extremity motions. The Trunk Control Measurement Scale, Pediatric Balance Scale, and GMFM-88 were outcome measures. Results showed a 32.7% improvement in trunk control, a 2-point increase in balance, and a 6.25% total improvement in GM skills.

Conclusion: This case report demonstrates a positive response to the MPE intervention in a 6-year-old child with CP, with improvements in trunk control, balance, and gross motor skills. Although cause and effect cannot be established based on a case report, the interventions contributed to improved trunk and balance control. Further studies are warranted to determine whether the intervention effectively treats young children with CP and moderate impairments.

Keywords: Pilates, Physical functional performance, Exercise program

Background

Cerebral palsy (CP) describes a spectrum of nonprogressive motor and postural impairments resulting from injury or abnormal fetal or infant brain development, leading to lifelong limitations in movement and functional activity [1,2]. Recent definitions further characterize CP as a group of permanent disorders of movement and posture development, attributed to non-progressive disturbances in the developing brain, which result in activity limitations [3]. Contemporary literature also recognizes CP as a lifelong neurodevelopmental condition that frequently co-occurs with disturbances in sensation, perception, cognition, communication, and behavior, as well as epilepsy and musculoskeletal complications [4].

The prevalence of CP is estimated to be about 2 cases per 1000 live births in high-income countries and up to about 112:1000 in preterm births born before 28 weeks of gestation [2]. It is well documented that children with CP have deficits in postural control and overall movement that impact the performance of daily activities [1-5].

Postural control (PC) is a complex process initiated in early development that takes time to develop. It allows for maintaining an upright body using anticipatory and automatic postural adjustments within varying sensory

environments [6-8]. Anticipatory adjustments involve sensory feedback to initiate necessary changes in the trunk and extremities to maintain upright after a movement has occurred [9]. Anticipatory postural adjustments (APAs) are pre-programmed, feedforward mechanisms that activate trunk and limb musculature in preparation for voluntary movement, allowing individuals to maintain stability before the movement is initiated [10]. These adjustments are primarily coordinated by cortical regions, with modulatory input from the cerebellum and basal ganglia [10,11]. In individuals with cerebral palsy (CP), particularly those with spastic or dyskinetic subtypes, the timing, magnitude, and coordination of APAs are often impaired due to early damage to these neural structures. Studies using electromyography and motion analysis have shown delayed or absent muscle activation patterns in children with CP during tasks, suggesting deficits in cortical motor planning and cerebellar timing mechanisms [12,13]. These impairments contribute to inefficient movement strategies and increased fall risk during functional activities.

Automatic postural adjustments occur after an unexpected external perturbation to restore equilibrium [14]. These rapid feedback responses are mediated primarily through subcortical pathways, including the vestibulospinal and reticulospinal tracts, with contributions from the brainstem

and cerebellum [14]. Children with CP often show exaggerated, poorly timed, or inappropriate automatic postural responses, likely due to abnormal integration of sensory input and impaired descending motor control [12,13]. Furthermore, the inability to efficiently switch between anticipatory and automatic strategies further limits adaptive motor control during functional activities.

Interventions such as task-specific training and balance-focused therapy have shown promise in enhancing postural control in CP by targeting both anticipatory and automatic mechanisms [6-8]. Understanding the neural and functional limitations of these systems in CP is critical for designing effective rehabilitation strategies aimed at improving functional mobility and reducing falls. Trunk control is a critical component of PC since it provides the necessary stable base of support during the execution of functional and dynamic activities of the extremities [15].

There is evidence that compensatory and primary trunk control deficits exist in children with CP [16,17]. Numerous studies have focused on assessing and addressing deficits in trunk control in children with CP to improve postural control, balance, gait, and gross motor skills [18-20]. Although there is support and evidence for focusing on trunk strength and control in children with CP, there needs to be more evidence-based data or recommendations on how best to accomplish this, especially in younger children.

Pilates consists of stretching, strengthening, and coordination exercises. Traditional Pilates is based on six fundamental principles: breathing, concentration, control, centering, precision, and fluidity [21]. Several studies have demonstrated the positive effects of Pilates-based training on adult populations: improved balance, reduced fall risk, improved strength, endurance, and proprioception [22,23]. Additionally, some studies have shown the benefit of Pilates training for young children [24,25]. Pilates' has been shown to stimulate sensorimotor pathways and promote cortical reorganization, which is a key mechanisms of neuroplasticity [26]. Neuroplasticity can be defined as the brain's ability to reorganize itself by forming new neural connections in response to injury or training [27]. Early intervention is critical in pediatric neurorehabilitation due to the heightened neuroplastic potential of the developing brain [27]. Evidence indicates that early motor training can lead to functional improvements and cortical reorganization in children with cerebral palsy [28, 29]. Pilates, in particular, has been shown to stimulate sensorimotor pathways and promote cortical reorganization, aligning with the key mechanisms of neuroplasticity [26]. Incorporating Pilates-based therapy during sensitive developmental windows offers structured sensory-motor input that can accelerate the recovery of movement patterns, improve proprioception, and reduce the risk of long-term functional limitations. These findings support the rationale for integrating targeted interventions like Pilates early in development to maximize therapeutic benefit and improve long-term outcomes in children with neurological impairments [26,30].

In recent years, focusing on postural control deficits in children with CP, a few studies have examined Pilates' effects in this population [20]. Although most of these studies have demonstrated the benefits of Pilates, the difficulty has been in determining if improved outcomes came from Pilates or conventional therapy. Additionally, the typical study population was 7 years or older, leaving questions regarding the benefit for the younger children [31-33]. Ozturk and Unver [34] demonstrated that Pilates improved children's postural evaluation and physical fitness in a subject group older than 7.

Additionally, it is an entertaining alternate physical activity for this population [34]. Pilates-based rehabilitation (PBR) is an intervention that incorporates the principles of Pilates into the rehabilitation setting. To succeed, modifications must be made to allow patients to perform safely

while benefiting from Pilates. One of the benefits of PBR is that mat-based activities can be incorporated without the need for specific equipment, which is often costly and space-prohibitive in these settings [20]. In contrast traditional core stabilization programs rely on repetitive isometric holds while Pilates exercises promote continuous feed forward activation of trunk musculature, enhancing anticipatory postural adjustments critical for maintaining equilibrium during movement [17,35].

Studies show that Pilates can improve postural control and physical fitness in adults and children of varying populations [31-34, 36-38]. It is acknowledged that children with CP have deficits in postural control that should be addressed to improve functional outcomes [17-20]. Therefore, this case report aims to demonstrate the potential benefits of a PBR program on trunk control and subsequent balance and gross motor skills in a child with spastic, diplegic CP.

Case Report

Patient history and systems review

The subject of this case report was a 6-year-old student with the diagnosis of cerebral palsy (CP) with moderate impairment, classified as a level II on the Gross Motor Function Classification System (GMFCS) [39,40]. She was diagnosed with cerebral palsy at the age of two by a neurologist based on a brain MRI scan. She could walk with a device at around three years of age. She was otherwise healthy with no surgical interventions, and no medications were taken. The subject was originally referred for a physical therapy evaluation in the school system with concerns she was unable to walk independently and was falling frequently. She participated in general education classes with no accommodation for academics, indicating normal cognition. She required assistance with her hand being held to walk and struggled to maintain her balance with frequent episodes of falling. She came initially to the school system at the age of five and was referred to physical therapy at that time. She was five years old when her initial physical therapy evaluation was completed, and she was seen for 10 treatments to address range of motion and strength deficits and improve her gait abilities. While the subject demonstrated improved ability to get up from the floor on her own and walk shorter distances without falling and participated in recess with her peers, she continued to require the walker and had episodes of falls within the classroom. For that reason, she was recommended to use a posture-control rolling walker when transitioning outside the classroom throughout her school day. This allowed her to ambulate with modified independence, reduced falls, and decreased fatigue. She could walk into the classroom with balance checks taken by holding onto items or placing her hands on the floor when stumbling. Despite this recommendation, the parent reported that the subject was carried by an adult or walked with a handheld in the community. The parent stated the subject had ankle braces and a walker in the past but did not use either within the past year. Despite the family's hesitation and the subject's use of the walker, they agreed that not using it resulted in significant safety concerns. The parent identified that the subject would be more independent without relying on an adult for transitions. The parent indicated that because of the overall challenge with functional activities such as walking, they wanted to see what physical therapy intervention could offer at this point.

The educationally relevant, functional physical therapy evaluation revealed the child had spasticity in her quadriceps and gastrocnemius bilaterally with resistance to dorsiflexion noted in both ankles impacting her gait and balance, decreased range of motion in her ankles, reduced strength in her legs and trunk as well as gait deviations consistent with the diagnosis of cerebral palsy (Table 1). Her gait pattern was one of reduced efficiency with a slower pace and shuffling feet with minimal heel contact, reduced stride length consistent with increased tone in hip flexors and plantar flexors with equines position of feet on the left side more than right. Fatigue decreased left leg clearance, resulting in trips and falls. The subject was

seen for one year to address a range of motion and strength deficits, decreased balance, and gait abilities. Improving her endurance was achieved by gradually increasing ambulation distances throughout the school day.

Table 1. Relevant Objective Findings. DF= dorsal flexion, PROM= passive range of motion, IR= internal rotation, ER = external rotation, R2=Full slow range, R1=Range at which catch felt with increased velocity motion, deg= degrees, sec= seconds

Findings	Initial Evaluation	Reassessment 1	Reassessment 2
Ankle DF PROM with knee neutral	Left: 5deg Right: 8 deg	Bilateral: 10 deg	No change
Ankle DF PROM with knee flexed 90 degrees	Left:10 deg Right:12 deg	Left:15 deg Right: 25 deg	No change
LE PROM hip flex/ext IR/ER Knee flex/ext	Full Range Bilaterally	No change	No change
Functional Strength Tasks	Supine flexion: 10 sec. hold Prone extension: 20 sec. hold Wall sit: 10 sec. hold Transfers from the floor to standing with use of both hands on the floor and plantigrade position (squat).	Supine flexion: 20 sec hold Prone extension: 30 sec. hold Wall sit: 20 sec. hold Transfers from floor to standing with one foot leading and both hands on the floor	Supine flexion: 30+ sec hold Prone extension: 30+ sec hold Wall sit: 30 sec. hold Transfers from floor to standing with one foot leading and both hands on the leading leg (thigh)
Modified Ashworth Scale ^{A,B}	Quadriceps: Left 1+ Right 1 Gastrocnemius: Left 2 Right 1 Adductors: Left 1 Right 1 Hamstrings: Left 1 Right 1	No Change	No Change
Tardieu Spasticity Angle Plantarflexors ^{B,C} (R2-R1)	Left:15 degrees (5-(-10)) Right: 3 degrees (8-5) Muscle quality: 2	Left:20 degrees (10-(-10)) Right: 0 degrees (10-10) Muscle Quality: 2	No Change

She presented for a reevaluation at the age of 6. While the subject demonstrated improved ability compared to the last evaluation regarding getting up from the floor independently, she can walk shorter distances without falling and participate more in recess with her peers; she continued to require the walker and had episodes of falls within the classroom. The subject stated her goal was to be able to walk without the walker, and while the parent was concerned about falls, she expressed the same goal during the annual review. The mom reported that her child was not receiving outpatient physical therapy due to a lack of insurance.

Initial clinical impression

The subject presented with a history of CP after one year of Physical therapy care in the school system. Upon reevaluation, she reported difficulties with sitting, her endurance, range of motion in the lower extremities (LE), strength in the LEs, spasticity in the LEs, and balance skills for transitions to and from the floor (Table 1). No red flags were identified, and a physical therapy reevaluation was indicated because she continued to experience

falls in the classroom and required the walker for longer transitions. It was decided to assess more specific deficits impacting progress, such as trunk control.

Examination

Since the child's reported difficulties with sitting, decreased endurance, limited lower extremity range of motion and strength, spasticity, and challenges with balance during transitions and walking activities, it was necessary to select outcome measures that comprehensively assess these impairments. The Trunk Control Measurement Scale was chosen because it is a validated tool specifically designed to assess both static and dynamic trunk control in children with CP, which directly relates to the child's difficulties maintaining upright posture and dynamic trunk control [40, 41]. The Pediatric Balance Scale was included as it evaluates balance through a range of functional tasks such as standing, reaching, and transitioning between positions, activities that mirror the child's difficulties with transfers and postural stability [42]. Lastly, the Gross Motor Function Measure-88 was selected due to its strong reliability and validity in assessing gross motor abilities in children with CP, including rolling, sitting, crawling, standing, and walking, areas in which the child showed functional limitations [43-46]. Together, these outcome measures provide an evidence-based assessment aligned with the subject's clinical presentation and are sensitive to identify changes in function following intervention.

Trunk Control Measurement Scale

The Trunk Control Measurement Scale (TCMS) was developed to address the unique abilities of children with CP to capture aspects of both static and dynamic sitting balance, with the latter being divided into selective movement control and dynamic reaching [41]. It has been proven a reliable and clinically relevant assessment for children aged 5 years and older with different neurological impairments [42]. The TCMS has 15 items and a total score of 58. It evaluates the trunk as a stable base with a static portion (total score of 20) and a dynamic aspect of trunk control (38). A higher score indicates better performance. The student received a score of 17 out of 20 for static sitting with difficulties pertaining to the measure requiring her to cross her leg over the other (Table 2). For dynamic sitting balance, she scored 6 out of 28 for selective movement control and 10 out of 10 for dynamic reaching. This is 33 out of 58 points and is in a low-performance range. By dividing trunk control into specific categories, this scale gives insight into the strengths and weaknesses of a child's trunk performance and provides invaluable clinical use for targeted interventions [41].

Table 2: TCMS test scores; Change of 6 points (10%) considered true change

TCMS subscales	Pre-intervention scores	Post-intervention scores	Percentile Change
Static sitting balance Items 1-5=20 points total	17/20	20/20	15%
Dynamic sitting balance Items 6-12=28 points total (Selective Movement control)	6/28	25/28	67.8%
Dynamic reaching Items 13-15=10 points total (equilibrium reactions)	10/10	10/10	0%
Overall Total Score 58 points total	33/58	52/58	32.7%

Pediatric Berg Scale

The Pediatric Balance Scale (PBS) is a modification of the Berg Balance Scale for school-aged children with mild to moderate impairments that assesses balance through 14 tasks in various postures [42]. Scores on the scale range from 0 to 56, with higher scores indicating better balance. It has been shown to have good test-retest and interrater reliability for this population with an ICC = 0.997 [42]. Clinical observations support content validity in that items assessed are routinely performed in this population and used by physical therapists in the school setting [42]. The subject obtained 43 out of 56 points, which is 77% (Table 3). This demonstrates impairment as noted by typical values of 53.8 ± 2.49 for her age (91-100%) [42]. The areas of difficulty pertained to single leg stance, narrowed base stance, stepping onto a stool, and reaching forward in standing.

Table 3: PBS test scores; MCID PBS Static (1.47-2.92), PBS Dyn (2.23-2.92), PBS Total (3.66-5.93)

PBS subscales	Pre-intervention scores	Post-intervention scores	Percentile Change
Static Items 1-6=24 total points	24/24	24/24	0%
Dynamic Items 7-14=32 total points	19/32	21/32	6.25%
Total Score 56 total points	43/56	45/56	3.57%

Gross Motor Function Measure-88 items (GMFM-88)

Gross motor performance was assessed using the GMFM-88, which is commonly used for children with CP [43]. It includes 88 items in five dimensions, from lying and rolling to standing, walking, and running. The higher the score in a dimension, the better the gross motor performance. The relative reliability of the GMFM-88 is excellent (ICCs=.952-1.00), with this measure proving to be reliable and responsive for the measurement of gross motor function in children with CP [44-46]. Only the Standing and Walking dimensions (D & E) were assessed, and the scores were presented as percentages. This was decided because these areas are known to impact children with CP at Level 2 on the GMFCS and best reflect the functional level of the subject. The student obtained 89.74% and 54.17% scores for Standing (D) and Walking, Running, and jumping Dimension (E), respectively (Table 4). While she has some challenges in the standing dimension, she struggles most in the Walking, Running, and Jumping Dimensions with a significantly reduced percentile score. The GMFM includes gross motor skills mastered by typically developing children at or below the age of 5 [47].

Table 4: GMFM scores; MCID 2.8 and 4.5 for medium and large effect respectively

GMFM-88 Dimension	Pre-intervention scores	Post-intervention scores	Percentile Change
D:Standing	35/39 (89.74%)	35/39 (89.74%)	0%
E:Walking, Running, Jumping	39/72 (54.17%)	48/72 (66.67%)	12.5%
Dimension Goal Total Score	143.91/2=71.95%	156.41/2=78.20%	6.25%

Clinical Impression

The student displayed decreased range of motion, strength, and spasticity

in bilateral LEs. Her balance skills for transitions to and from the floor were impaired and deficits in selective trunk control impacted overall balance and gross motor performance. Her endurance, range of motion in the lower extremities (LE), strength in the LEs, spasticity in the LEs, and balance skills for transitions to and from the floor (Table 1). Previous interventions to improve functional balance and mobility yielded minimal gains toward independent mobility and reduced falls. The parent and child identified that walking better was their objective. Pilates-based exercises focus on improving control of the core musculature, an area of weakness for the subject. Therefore, a 10-week Pilates-based intervention focusing on selective trunk control would assist in attaining the therapy goals of improved dynamic control of the LEs, improve transfers, improve static and dynamic sitting balance, and ambulate independently with reduced falls (Table 5).

Table5: Modified-Pilates Exercise

Modified Hundreds 10 sets of 5 inhales and 5 exhales, up to count of 100 In a supine position with the head, position lifted 30 degrees and two lower limbs lifted together in a tabletop position of 90:90 degrees, hips and knees	In a supine position with the head, position lifted 30 degrees and two lower limbs lifted together in a tabletop position of 90:90 degrees, hips and knees
Shoulder bridge 5-8 times	In supine, hook lying position, raising pelvis off the mat
Modified single-leg circles 2-3 times through	In supine on a mat, draw a circle with each lower extremity 10 times in each direction per leg (Modified to allow resting foot on the mat for added stability)
Alternate toe touch 5 times to each side	In the supine position, try to touch the toes with both hips and knees in 90 degrees flexion, alternating sides
Modified Roll like a ball 5-10 times	Begin sitting on bottom with knees bent and held toward chest by arms, roll to back slowly keeping chin close to chest. Therapist assists at feet as needed to come back to sitting while maintaining form
Scissors 2-3 times through	In supine, keeping hands flat on the mat, move legs up and down like scissors trying to keep legs straight. Alternate while counting to 10
Bicycle 2-3 times through	In supine, alternate bending and straightening legs like riding a bicycle. Count to 10
Saw 4-6 times each side	Sitting with legs spread to each side, move left hand over right leg and then move right hand over left leg like sawing motion
Mermaid 3-5 times to each side	Sitting on mat with legs folded to the left, lift right arm and bend toward the left side. Stay for a few moments and then change sides.
Plank on Elbows 3-5 times	Prone on elbows keeping pelvis, hips and knees off the mat while pressing through elbows into the mat. Hold 10-20 seconds

Clamshell 10-20 times	Lying on side with hips and knees flexed approximately 30 degrees, rotating top leg out and up (opening clam shell) and close. Repeat on the other side.
Hip abduction 10-20 times	Lying on side with bottom leg bent to comfortable position, keeping hips facing forward with no rotation in spine lift top leg to side and back down. Repeat on other side
Leg circles 3-5 times	Lying on side lifting top leg and making circles in each direction 10 times. Repeat the other side.
*Ball Wall Squats 5-10 times	Standing with back against a ball on the wall, slide down slowly, pause, and return to standing.
*Elastic band leg lift and lower 5-10 times *Elastic band leg lift and lower 5-10 times	Standing with back against the wall for balance with elastic resistance band under one foot and holding the band in both hands for resistance, lift leg slowly and push back down to the floor. Repeat on the other side.

*Indicate exercises added the last 3 weeks of program

Intervention

The subject completed a 10-week Modified-Pilates Exercise (MPE) program designed for specific needs as determined her examination. The first 7 weeks focused on supine core control with dynamic extremity activities, supine lumbopelvic stabilization, seated core control with dynamic extremity activities and plank core control. Three of the 12 Pilates exercises were modified in such a way that additional support was provided in certain positions, so the child was able to perform the exercises (Table 2). The last three weeks two standing exercises were added that focused on upright core control and dynamic strength strengthening exercises (Table 2). Due to the child's younger age and the school system setting, sessions were kept to 30 minutes. Encouragement and motivation of stickers were given upon completion of sessions. The child was seen in one-on-one sessions with a pediatric physical therapist once weekly for ten sessions. An introduction and explanations regarding the benefits and principles of Pilates were given in a language the subject could understand in the first session. The therapist guided exercises in proper form with verbal reminders and physical prompts as needed due to the child's limitations with specific activations of isolated muscle groups. Prompts were graded as the child was able to activate on her own. In addition, guides such as a paper windmill and feather were used to encourage proper breathing techniques during exercises. No adverse events occurred during the interventions, with the subject instructed to communicate if she experienced any pain.

Basic level Pilates was performed since the child was younger and had known neurological deficits. All exercises started at half repetitions and progressed over the weeks to full number as the subject maintained proper control. The last two exercises performed in standing were added in the last 3 weeks of the program when the subject understood how to control and coordinate motion in standing. (Table 2).

It is interesting to note that while no specific home exercise program was issued, the student became familiar with the exercises and would direct the order of performance as the weeks progressed. She was eager and willing to perform the exercises and stated she had been doing them at home and was teaching her family members to do them. This demonstrates motivation and that for this subject, MPE was a fun activity to participate in.

Results

After ten physical therapy sessions focusing on the MPE program designed for the subject's specific needs, she improved the TCMS by scoring 52 out of 58 points. This includes maximal scores in the static sitting balance and dynamic reaching subscales (20 out of 20 points and 10 out of 10 points, respectively) Dynamic sitting balance improved from 6 to 25 out of 28 points (Table 2 and Figure 1). The more typical range for her age is based on a study that demonstrated that typically developing children between the ages of 8 and 10 scored lower than submaximal and maximal in this subscale [41]. Heyrman et al. [41] report that this skill may have maturation effects since higher scores were noted in children 11 and older. The change in her total score of 19 points was considerable compared to her pre-intervention score of 33 out of 58. It has been determined that a change of 6 points is considered a true change.

Figure 1. Bar graph displaying the outcome measure as a percentage of change from, pre intervention to post intervention for the PBS, GMFM-88, and the TCMS measures.

She scored 24 out of 24 on the pre and post intervention measures on the PBS with no recorded change. However, there was a total change of 2 points from the preintervention score on the PBS for the dynamic item of placing an alternate foot on a stool. This improved from 19 to 21 points out of 32 (Table 3 and Figure 1). This change is considered within the minimal detectable change (MDC) for a dynamic score cutoff of 0.96 and a total score of 1.59, indicating an actual change [48]. However, it is lower than the minimally clinically important difference (MCID) cutoff for children with CP of 2.92 and 5.83 for dynamic and total scores, respectively [48]. The observed improvements in static and dynamic sitting balance partially met her therapeutic goal.

The subject did not demonstrate a change in the Standing Dimension of the GMFM-88, with a score of 89.74% (Table 4 and Figure 1). She demonstrated a change of 12.5% in the Walking, Running, and Jumping Dimension of the GMFM-88. She improved from 39 point to 48 points out of 72. Additionally, she demonstrated an improved ability to walk in a straight line, step over a stick with each foot leading, run, jump vertically (up) and horizontally (forward), and go upstairs with alternating patterns with a railing. The two goal dimensions determined to be the focus areas for the intervention showed a change in total scores of 6.25%. This finding correlated with the improved ability of the child to walk independently. While it is difficult to assess MCID in children with such varying abilities as CP, in the original work with the GMFM-88, parents, and therapists identified a gain of approximately 5-7 percent as a "medium" positive change [48]. Oeffering et al. [49] determined that the MCID for the walking, running, and jumping dimensions is 2.8 and 4.5 for medium and large effects, respectively, in children with Level II on GMFCS. This is similar to the findings of Storm et al. [49], who found the MCID values for this dimension in this population to be between 0.3% and 4.9%. Using this information, the difference in score for this dimension of 6.25% represents a meaningful

change. In another study, it was noted that the standard error of measurement (SEM) for the walking, running, and jumping dimensions is 2.12, and the smallest real difference (SRD) is 4.16 [45, 50,51]. Therefore, her change of 9 points is not due to change and can likely represent a real difference.

Functionally, the subject could walk without a walker throughout her school day and campus distances without falling. This improvement met the parent and child's treatment objective and the therapeutic goal of improved dynamic control of the LEs and ambulating independently. She could perform a 6-inch step without arm support and jump vertically 3 inches and forward 2 inches. She expressed excitement about walking without the walker, and staff reported noticing her increased independence throughout her school day and that she was no longer concerned that she would fall.

Discussion

This case report details how an MPE program can be used as a physical therapy intervention with a young child with spastic diplegic CP within the educational setting. Improvements were found in trunk control, balance, and GM skills after implementing a 10-week program. More importantly, the subject met her desired goal of walking independently. The result of this case report concurs with previous reports of improved functional abilities after interventions targeting trunk control in children with CP [52-54]. The TCMS has been identified as a validated and reliable tool to evaluate trunk control in children with varying types of CP aged 8-15 [54]. The TCMS is performed in sitting to isolate trunk control better and reduce the impact of compensatory movements caused by lower limb pathology. The subject in this case report was only six, and the total TCMS and subscale scores differed between varying topographies of children with CP. They were correlated with the severity level of impairment on the GMFCS. This correlation this concurs with the findings of Kallem et al. [55], who identified a significant relationship between the TCMS and the GMFCS. Typically, static sitting balance is only mildly impaired in children with hemiplegia and diplegia, children with diplegia typically demonstrate increased difficulties with trunk control when abducting their lower limbs. This concurs with the findings in this case and seems consistent with the report of selective movement control being an area of pathology.

Children with spastic diplegic CP have difficulties in maintaining trunk control during active leg movement. Therefore, interventions should improve the trunk's ability to counterbalance disturbances caused by lower limb movements [54]. Additionally, interventions to improve the trunk's ability to move actively in controlled and deliberate manners in all three planes of motion could improve the deficits seen in dynamic reaching. Pilates as an exercise modality focuses on controlled movements, promoting flexibility, joint mobility, and core strength. It enhances slow, deliberate movements, emphasizing trunk control [56]. Therefore, Pilates can benefit young children with CP and improve balance, coordination, and mobility. Although cause and effect can not be determined using case reports, the subject, in this case, demonstrated gains in trunk control after a Pilates-based intervention focusing on the primary trunk control impairments found with the TCMS, which supports the use of this intervention in ambulatory children with CP. This concurs with the findings of Adiguzel et al. [33] who identified that Pilates positively could affect trunk control in children with CP.

In this case, the subject demonstrated decreased trunk control, as evidenced by the TCMS, which seems consistent with previous reports. Heyrman et al [53] compared head and trunk kinematics during gait in children with diplegic CP representing Levels I and II on the GMFCS with typically developing (TD) children. The children with CP in both Levels had impaired trunk control compared to TD peers. Level II demonstrated increased movements in the head and trunk, while Level I and TD chil-

dren had neutral head positions throughout gait. Both Levels demonstrate decreased thoracic kyphosis and increased lumbar lordosis during stance and gait swing compared to TD children [52]. Additionally, Heyrman et al. [52] reported altered trunk movements during gait in both levels of children with CP. Therefore, altered trunk movements during gait should not be considered solely compensatory in response to lower limb deficits and might reflect underlying trunk control pathology. The main focus of the intervention for the subject in this case was improving trunk control. Based on the observed improvement, the MPE program resulted in gains in trunk control. Therefore, Pilates should be considered a viable intervention for this population.

Previously reported studies have provided guidelines for focusing on interventions specific to the areas of trunk pathology identified in testing. However, they do not outline specific exercises [14-16]. Evidence shows that Pilates can improve PC, balance, GM skills, and gait in children with CP [20,31,33]. Kallem et al [55] previously identified that the GMFM-88 scores are significantly related to trunk control. Based on changes in the GMFM-88, the pilates intervention resulted in clinically significant improvement in the ability to walk in a straight line, step over a stick with each foot leading, run, jump vertically (up) and horizontally (forward), and go upstairs with alternating patterns with a railing in our subject. This concurs with the findings of Elnagger et al. [20], who demonstrated the benefit of Pilates-based core strengthening, plyometric-based muscle loading, and their combination in children with unilateral CP (ULCP) ages 12-18 with gains in PC, balance, and mobility. Additionally, Abd-Elfattah et al. [31] identified that a 10-week program of Pilates as an adjunct to physical therapy in children aged 7-9 with diplegic CP resulted in more effective improvements in balance and GM skills than with conventional therapy alone. Adiguzel et al. [33] reported that children aged 7-14 with CP of varying types showed improvements in trunk, PC, gait, and balance after 8 weeks of MPE compared to NDT-based therapy. A single case report by Dos Santos et al. [57] identified that reformer Pilates for eight weeks in a child with ULCP appeared to result in improvements in bilateral lower extremity strength (more so on the paretic side) and the child's ability to control his posture increased as evidenced by decreased displacement of body's center of pressure during anterior-posterior and medial-lateral oscillations in static standing.

No previous reports have evaluated the benefit of MPE intervention on children under 7. Therefore, this case report adds to the body of knowledge regarding the benefit of MPE in younger children with diplegic CP when treatment interventions focus on trunk control, balance, and GM skills. Our findings do not concur with those of Coman et al [32], who determined that Pilates-based exercises did not change lower limb or trunk kinematics during walking on level ground, uneven ground, and crossing an obstacle or balance parameters in ambulant children with CP. Although improvements in balance were identified, they were not clinically significant, and this might have been due to the ceiling effect of the Berg Balance Scale, which may have caused the test to be insensitive to changes in ambulatory children. The subject of our case report demonstrated improvements on the PBS with the task requiring trunk stabilization when actively moving her limb onto a stool and balance pertaining to standing with one foot in front of the other and standing on one foot. This agrees with the findings reported by Heyrman et al. [52], suggesting that children with CP will demonstrate improvements when addressing primary trunk deficits. However, underlying lower limb pathologies also affect function with closed-chain tasks. While the subject of this case demonstrated an improved ability to stabilize her trunk with active movement of her lower limb, the tasks of standing on one foot and a narrower base requiring more isolated use of ankle strategies for balance did not change. This is consistent with an ongoing pathology of the lower limb in children with diplegic CP [52,53]. The objective data of this case reflects that the subject has spasticity in her lower limbs.

The subject of this case demonstrates a deficit in selective movement control with significant improvements after 10 weeks of MPE. While this case did not evaluate gait parameters and cannot infer a change in gait kinematics, there was a meaningful change in trunk control that could have impacted her ability to walk independently. Pilates could have helped the subject learn to control her body since there is an emphasis on cognitive concentration and a "mind-body" connection with a slow, deliberate, and coordinated pace [58]. Although this case is only reporting on the changes in our subject based on a 10-week MPE program, long-term retention of Pilates benefits has been demonstrated and attributed to the fact that Pilates emphasizes neuromuscular re-education, postural alignment, and controlled movement patterns that enhance motor learning [59,60]. Future studies should evaluate the long-term benefit of Pilates for children with CP. Because the current MPE program was designed to build core strength and flexibility, this could have impacted trunk control and resulted in the most significant gains in this area through the TCMS [61, 62]. Even so, the clinically significant improvements in trunk control likely resulted in the functional gain in her ability to walk independently, balance, and perform GM skills. No long-term effects of the intervention in this case can be implied. Future research should demonstrate Pilates's short- and long-term benefits with young children with CP and identify specific intervention parameters.

Conclusions

Pilates appears to be a valuable rehabilitation technique for children with CP with mild to moderate impairments with higher functional skills. Although cause and effect can not be inferred and outcomes can not be generalized from a case report, the results offer preliminary evidence demonstrating clinically significant improvement in trunk control, balance, and GM skills after a 10-week program measured with the GMFM-88, TCMS, and PBS outcome measures. These findings support the use of Pilates in a younger child with CP. The MPE program was designed to address trunk deficits, which is beneficial. The subject met her personal goal of walking independently without needing a walker. High-quality longitudinal studies are needed to research outcomes that reflect a change in trunk control and gait and balance parameters using specific Pilates interventions designed to impact each topography of CP. This could inform evidence-based practice regarding the best interventions for trunk control and functional outcomes of balance, gait, and GM coordination.

Declaration of Table and Figures' Authenticity

All tables submitted have been created by the authors, who confirm that the images are original, have no duplication, and have not been previously published in whole or in part.

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